
Screening of Metabolites of Endophytic Fungi Isolated from Leaves of *Azadirachta indica* for Antimicrobial and Cytotoxic Activities

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Abstract Two endophytic fungi (AIn-L4 and AIn-L5) were isolated from the leaves of *Azadirachta indica*. The fungi were subjected to solid state fermentation on rice medium and the fungal secondary metabolites were extracted using ethyl acetate. The fungal extracts were screened for possible antimicrobial and cytotoxic activities. Also, some of the bioactive compounds of the extracts were detected using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) analysis. The result of the antimicrobial assay reveal that at 1 mg/mL, AIn-L5 extract showed mild antibacterial activity against *B. subtilis* and *S. typhi* with inhibition zone diameters of 4 and 5 mm respectively. Extract of AIn-L4 showed no activity against any of the test bacteria, and both fungal extracts showed no antifungal activity against the test fungi. Result of the cytotoxicity assay reveals that the extract of AIn-L4 showed 100% cytotoxic activity and completely inhibited the growth of mouse lymphoma cells L5178Y, while AIn-L5 showing no cytotoxic activity. The HPLC analysis of AIn-L4 extract revealed the presence of aureonitol, while AIn-L5 showed the presence of scytalone, cladosporin, and citreoisocoumarinol. The study showed that these endophytic fungi could be promising sources of novel bioactive compounds with pharmaceutical or industrial importance.

Keywords *Azadirachta indica*, endophytic fungi, secondary metabolites, antimicrobial and cytotoxic activities, HPLC analysis

Introduction

Endophytes are microorganisms that colonize asymptotically the intercellular and/or intracellular parts of healthy plants and play an important role in drug discovery [1]. It has been proven that endophytic microbes have the ability to produce the same or similar bioactive chemicals as those originated from their host plants [2,3]. This confirms fungal endophytes as potential alternatives to plants for the industrial production of valuable natural products.

Nigeria's rich plant biodiversity presents an enormous platform for researchers to explore in the area of bioprospecting without the destructive harvesting of plants, but by exploring their associated endophytic organisms for pharmaceutically and industrially important molecules [4]. Several studies on the endophytic fungal populations of Nigerian medicinal plants have confirmed the enormous potentials which abound in these organisms as sources of novel bioactive molecules [2-11].

Azadirachta indica (Meliaceae), commonly known as Neem, is an evergreen tree indigenous to India and Africa, and found in tropical regions of the world [12]. The plant has been in use since ancient times to treat a number of human ailments and also as household pesticide. Extracts from the bark, leaves, fruits and roots *A. indica* have been used to control leprosy, intestinal helminthosis and respiratory disorders [13-16]. Biologically active compounds isolated from different parts of the plant include: azadirachtin, meliacin, gedunin, salanin, nimbin, valassin, and many other derivatives of these compounds [17].

A. indica have been studied for their endophytic microbial populations and several endophytes producing bioactive natural products have been reported from the plant [12, 18-25]. The search for microorganisms of biotechnological interest based on the ethnobotanical pharmacology of the plants they are associated with represents an alternative to discover new microorganisms and bioactive molecules [26]. Based on these principles, the exploration of microorganisms from new ecological niches, such as endophytes, constitutes an important strategy for obtaining novel bioactive molecules with pharmaceutical or industrial applications.

In our search for biologically active molecules from endophytic fungi associated with Nigerian plants, this study was carried out to investigate the metabolites of endophytic fungi isolated from *A. indica* for antimicrobial and cytotoxic activities, and identify its constituents using HPLC.

Methods

Collection of Plant Materials

Healthy leaves of *A. indica* leaves were collected from their trees growing in their natural environments at Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria. Isolation of endophytic fungi from the plant leaves, solid state fermentation of the fungi and extraction of the fungal secondary metabolites were carried out using standard methods as described by Eze *et al.* [4].

Antimicrobial Assay

Antibacterial and antifungal assays of the endophytic fungal extracts were carried out using the agar well diffusion method described by Akpotu *et al.* [9]. A concentration of 1 mg/mL of the extracts was tested against laboratory strains of *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, and *Salmonella typhi* in the antibacterial assay; and against *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus fumigatus* in the antifungal assay. Gentamicin (10 µg/mL) and ketoconazole (50 µg/mL) were used as positive controls in the antibacterial and antifungal tests respectively, while DMSO was used as the negative control in both tests. The inhibition zone diameters (IZDs) produced by the extracts and controls against the test isolates were measured and recorded.

Cytotoxicity Assay

The cytotoxicity was tested against L5178Y mouse lymphoma cells using the MTT assay described by Ngwoke *et al.* [27]. Stock solutions of the endophytic fungal extracts were prepared in ethanol 96% (v/v). Exponentially growing cells were harvested, counted and diluted appropriately. From the cell suspension, 50 µL containing 3750 cells were pipetted into each of the 96-well microtiter plates. Subsequently, 50 µL of a solution of the test samples containing the appropriate concentration (10 µg/mL) was added to each well. The test plates were incubated at 37 °C with 5% CO₂ for 72 h. A solution of 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) was prepared at 5 mg/mL in phosphate buffered saline and from this solution, 20 µL was pipetted into each well. The yellow MTT penetrates the healthy living cells and, in the presence of mitochondrial dehydrogenases MTT is transformed to its blue formazan complex. After an incubation period of 3 h 45 min at 37°C in a humidified incubator with 5% CO₂, the medium was centrifuged (15 min, 20°C, 210 × g) with 200 µL DMSO, the cells were lysed to liberate the formazan product. After thorough mixing, the absorbance was measured at 520 nm using a scanning microliter spectrophotometer. The color intensity is correlated with the number of healthy living cells. All experiments were carried out in triplicates and repeated three times. Cell survival was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Survival \%} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of treated} - \text{Absorbance of culture medium}}{\text{Absorbance of untreated} - \text{Absorbance of culture medium}} \times 100$$

High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)

HPLC analysis of the endophytic fungal extracts was carried out as described by Eze *et al.* [4]. This was done using a Dionex P580 HPLC system coupled to a photodiode array detector (UVD340S, Dionex Softron GmbH, Germering, Germany). The separation column (125 × 4 mm; length × internal diameter) was prefilled with Eurospher-10 C18 (Knauer, Germany) and a linear gradient of nanopure water (adjusted to pH 2 by addition of formic acid) and methanol was used as eluent. Detection was set at 235 nm and the absorption peaks of the fungal extract were analyzed by comparing with those in the HPLC-UV/Vis database.

Results

Two endophytic fungi (AIn-L4 and AIn-L5) were isolated from the leaves of *A. indica*. The result of the antimicrobial assay of the endophytic fungal extracts (Table 1) reveal that at 1 mg/mL, extract of AIn-L5 showed mild antibacterial activity against *B. subtilis* and *S. typhi* with IZD of 4 and 5 mm respectively.. Extract of AIn-L4 showed no activity against any of the bacteria, and both fungal extracts showed no antifungal activity against the test fungi *C. albicans* and *A. fumigatus*.

Result of the cytotoxicity assay (Table 2) reveals that the extract of AIn-L4 showed 100% cytotoxic activity and completely inhibited the growth of mouse lymphoma cell L5178Y, with AIn-L5 showing no cytotoxic activity.

The HPLC analysis of the extract of AIn-L4 revealed the presence of aureonitol, while AIn-L5 showed the presence of scytalone, cladosporin, and citreoisocoumarinol.

The HPLC chromatogram of the fungal extracts, as well as the UV-spectra and chemical structures of detected compounds are presented in Figures 1 and 2.

Table 1: Results of the antimicrobial evaluation of the fungal extract showing the inhibition zone diameters (IZD) (mm) produced against test organisms

Test Organisms	AIn-L4	AIn-L5	Positive control	Negative control
	Gentamicin (10 µg/ml)			DMSO
<i>S. aureus</i>	0	0	17	0
<i>S. typhi</i>	0	5	21	0
<i>B. subtilis</i>	0	4	22	0
<i>E. coli</i>	0	0	16	0
Ketoconazole (50 µg/ml)				DMSO
<i>C. albicans</i>	0	0	17	0
<i>A. fumigatus</i>	0	0	4	0

Table 2: Cytotoxic activity of endophytic fungal extracts against L5178Y mouse lymphoma cells

Endophytic fungal extracts	Concentration (µg/mL)	% inhibition
AIn-L4	10	100
AIn-L5	10	0

Figure 1: HPLC chromatogram of AIn-L4 extract, UV Spectra and chemical structure of the detected bioactive compound - aureonitol (A)

Figure 2: HPLC chromatogram of AIn-L5 extract, UV Spectra and chemical structure of the detected bioactive compounds scytalone (B), cladosporin (C), and citreoisocoumarinol (D)

Discussion

From the result in Table 1, it can be seen that the extract of AIn-L5 showed mild antibacterial activity against *B. subtilis* and *S. typhi* with IZD of 4 and 5 mm respectively. This activity may be attributed to antimicrobial compounds present in the extract. Extract of AIn-L4 showed no antimicrobial activity against any of the test organisms. However, the extract of AIn-L4 demonstrated strong cytotoxic activity and completely inhibited the growth of mouse lymphoma cell L5178Y, with AIn-L5 showing no cytotoxic activity (Table 2).

HPLC analysis revealed the presence of several biologically active compounds in extracts of AIn-L4 and AIn-L5. Aureonitol, an antiviral compound, was detected in AIn-L4; while three other compounds (scytalone, cladosporin, and citreoisocoumarinol), with diverse biological properties, were detected in AIn-L5.

Aureonitol is a derivative of tetrahydrofuran derivative and has been shown to excellent antiviral activity against influenza A and B viruses [28]. Aureonitol has been isolated from different fungal species of the genus *Chaetomium* [28,29].

Scytalone has been previously isolated from several endophytic fungi which include *Cladosporium tenuissimum*, [30], *Annulohyphoxylon* sp. [1], *Phomopsis* sp. [31], and *Scytalidium* sp. [32]. Scytalone has been known as an intermediate in the biosynthesis of melanin, the dark pigment of many phytopathogenic fungi [31,33,34]. Melanin is specifically involved with the hyphal (appresoria) penetration into leaves, and cell walls [34]. It was also observed that at low concentrations scytalone increased the growth rate of cells within the foliar lamina and roots of *Arabidopsis thaliana* [35].

Citreoisocoumarinol, an isocoumarin derivative has been previously isolated from different endophytic fungi such as *Penicillium corylophilum* [36], *Nectria* sp. [37], and *Fusarium tricinctum* [38], and it has been reported to show α -glucosidase inhibitory activity [37]. Isocoumarins are prevalent in most natural products that exhibit a wide range of biological activities including anti-diabetic [39], antimicrobial [40], insecticidal [41], antiparasitic [42,43], cytotoxic [44], anti-inflammatory [45], and anti-angiogenic [46].

Cladosporin, another isocoumarin derivative detected with citreoisocoumarinol in AIn-L5, has been isolated from several endophytic fungi including *Cladosporium cladosporioides* [47,48] and *Eurotium* sp. [49]. It has been reported to show antiplasmodial [50], antifungal [48], antibacterial [47,49], insecticidal [41], and antitumor properties [48].

Citreoisocoumarinol and cladosporin with known antimicrobial properties [40,47,49], together with other undetected compounds, may be responsible for the antimicrobial activity exhibited by the extract from AIn-L5. The excellent cytotoxic activity exhibited by AIn-L4 extract may be due to undetected cytotoxic compounds present in the extract. This cytotoxic activity indicates the potential of this fungus in the discovery of lead anticancer agents. Since the discovery of the anticancer compound paclitaxel (Taxol®) from a fungal endophyte, *Taxomyces adreanae* [51], the potentials of fungal metabolites as the source of anticancer agents has remained high as a whole lot of them are at different phases of clinical trial [52].

The expression of these bioactive chemical constituents by the fungal endophytes is an indication that endophytes associated with *A. indica* may be potential sources of precursors for drug development.

Conclusion

This study show that endophytic fungi associated with *A. indica* could be a promising source of novel bioactive compounds with pharmaceutical or industrial importance. It is recommended that further research on these endophytic fungi and their metabolites be carried out in order to confirm and expand the data provided in this preliminary investigation.

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